

Vedic Astrology: Status of Biodiversity Ingrained

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Abstract

Plant World is significant in religions throughout the ages. Astrology is a traditional discipline dealing with Grahas (Planets), Rashis (Signs of Zodiac) and Nakshatras (Stars). Plants have been appropriated with these since Vedic period and still in vogue. These plant taxa are advised to worship for better human life. The present communication is aimed at knowing status of plant species associated with them. The researches carried out to date are also compared. Five plant species turned out to be exotic in origin. A necessity is reiterated to study the realm of Vedic astrology collaboratively involving knowledgeable experts in plant taxonomy, history, astrology, Sanskrit and English languages to avoid further ambiguity.

Key words: Vedic Astrology, Sacred Plants, Biodiversity

1.0 Introduction:

The review of literature indicates that the Aryans migrated to India between 2300 to 1750 BC. It also seems that Harappan civilization began to decline in about 1750 BC. This decline was connected with the arrival of the Aryans in some way in Indian territory. The Vedic literature also indicates that the Aryans were keen observer of the biodiversity of the newly acquired Indian region. During their stay, they compiled vast literature- the four Vedas containing over thousands of hymns and songs in Sanskrit. A spirit of enquiry is certainly discernible in the Vedic texts. This amount of literature contains decisively interesting science potential. The Aryans were concerned about agriculture, environment, forestry, biodiversity, animal husbandry and such other issues in

their ambiance. To the Aryans, study of biodiversity of this country became a self-imposed task being strangers in this land.

The system of Vedic (Hindus) astrology is a way of predicting one's destiny based on the position of the planets and stars. It originated from the Vedas. It is still prevalent today and also called 'Jyotisha'. This discipline is being consulted by Hindus prior to persuasion of any life endeavor or hardship. Astrology is thus a traditional discipline which is usually concerned with nine Grahas (Planets), twelve Rashis (Signs of Zodiac) and 27 Nakshatras (Stars). These are thought influential on the human life (cf. Frawley, 1992). To regain fortune, some plants of medicinal virtues selected based on astrology and horoscope of a person, are worshipped to diminish bad effects of plants and stars (cf. Kodoliar *et al.*, 2023; Parihar and Sharma, 2021; Sharma and Johari, 2023). The plant species have been also critically investigated on scientific basis. However, these remained unstudied from the point of status of biodiversity. The plant species ingrained in Vedic astrology is being analysed in this communication.

2.0 Methodology:

The primary ancient literary source is available through: (i) Rigveda (cf. Wilson, 1857; Sharma, 1993), (ii) Atharveda (cf. Griffith, 1968; Devichand, 1995), (iii) Raja Nighantu (cf. Tripathy, 2010) for tracing the concept of plant species and astrology. Apart from these, secondary sources have been also consulted (cf. Sikarwar, 2020; Kodoliar, 2023; Sharma, 2021; Mishra, 2018) etc.

The Sanskrit plant names embedded in these scripts or sources are equated with the recent (Latin) botanical names and assigned to their respective families. Their status regarding nativity, habit, wildness or cultivated nature is documented in the Table-I. The data so accrued is analysed in the perspective of biodiversity and its antiquity, apart from plant invasion (bioinvasion).

3.0 Results and Discussion

The present authors analysed elements of biodiversity ingrained in Grahas (Planets), Rashis (Sign of Zodiac) and Nakshatras (Stars) tabulated in the Table-I, II and III respectively. They are analysed as the following:

The Grahas are associated with total 09 plant species, all being angiosperms. They pertain to 08 genera and 06 families, of which the monocotyledons shared minor role (02 species, 02 genera, 01 family). The dicotyledons played a major role (07 species, 06 genera, 05 families). Their habitat categorization is thus: trees (05 species), shrubs (01 species) and herbs (02 species). Their status regarding wildness or cultivated is also determined. They are either wild (08 species), other one (01 species) is found under cultivation as also round wild in nature. All are indigenous to India except two species viz., *Calotropis gigantea* (L.) R.Br. and *Achyranthes aspera* L. (cf. Table-I).

The Rashis (Sign of Zodiac) are integrated with total 12 angiospermic species, all being dicotyledons (11 genera and 07 families). The dicotyledons thus have a major and total role in association with the Rashis. Interestingly, all of them are tree species. These are wild (05 species), cultivated (03 species) and either wild or cultivated (04 species). All species are indigenous to India (cf. Table-II).

Nakshatras (Stars) are associated with total 33 species, one species being a gymnosperm. The angiosperms are either dicotyledons (30 species, 27 genera, 20 families) or monocotyledons (02 species, 02 genera, 02 families). They belong to different habitat categories such as: (i) trees (30 species), shrubs (01 species), climbers (02 species) and herb (01 species). They run wild exclusively in nature (17 species) or being cultivated exclusively (09 species). There are few ones which are both, either wild or cultivated (07 species). Interestingly, some species are associated twice with some Nakshatras (Stars) e.g. *Mesua ferrea*, *Prosopis cineraria*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Saraca asoca*, *Mangifera indica* and *Cocos nucifera*. However, *Azadirachta indica* is associated with three different Nakshatras (Stars). Out of 30 species, five species are exotic (cf. Table-III).

Nakshatra trees (Birth Star Trees) have been investigated in various realms of researches and knowledge such as human physiology, medicinal botany, phenology, religious beliefs, spiritually, apart from astrology and astronomy (Ramesh and Radha, 2002; Sikarwar, 2020; Kodoliar *et al.*, 2023; Sharma and Johari, 2023; Parihar and Sharma, 2018; Mishra, 2018; Frawley, 1992; Sanagala *et al.*, 2022; Balamurugan *et al.* 2019).

Ambiguity in case of assignment of trees to each Nakshatra (Star) have clearly surfaced because of certain reasons such as: (i) errors in translation from Sanskrit scripts to English version,

(ii) equivalent Latin (botanical/scientific) names of Sanskrit names, (iii) synonymy of Sanskrit plant names, (iv) varied versions of some Puranas in different contents. This has resulted in revealing increased number of Nakshatra trees e.g. (i) gleaned from Skanda Purana, Narada Purana, Brihat Sushruta, etc. revealed 27 stars and 65 trees, etc. (ii) Prakash Velu studied ancient Tamil literature shed light on 27 stars and 108 trees (cf. Sanagala *et al.*, 2022). The present authors, therefore, urge that such investigations should be executed by a collaborative team of research workers and knowledgeable experts in Sanskrit *vis-à-vis* English languages, well versed taxonomists, astronomers, astrologers, historians, etc.

Total 12 Rashis (Signs of Zodiac) are recognised in Indian culture as per Vedic astrology. These signs (Table-II) are decided based on the positions of the planets, the sun and moon on the ecliptic during one's birth period and also at particular period of life. A person is expected to worship a tree associated with his Rashi. The influence of plants, sun or moon is said to be as the following (cf. Chauhan and Chauhan, 2019).

Table 01. Tree in Worshipped

Sr. No.	Rashi	Influence By	Tree To Be Worshipped
1	Aries, Scorpio	Mars	<i>Senegalia catechu</i>
2	Taurus, Libra	Venus	<i>Ficus recemosa</i>
3	Gemini, Virgo	Mercury	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>
4	Cancer	Moon	<i>Butea monosperma</i>
5	Leo	Sun	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>
6	Sagittarius, Pisces	Jupiter	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>
7	Capricorn, Aquarius	Saturn	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i>

The Grahas (Planets) are thought integrated with the administration of 'Natural Law' and govern the entire universe. The nava (nine) Grahas (Planets) are worshipped for better fortune or considered useful in combating bad fortune. Each plant species associated with them especially appropriated ones influence one's field energy. The positions of the Grahas at the time of one's birth and their movements in the celestial globe have bearing on systems of mankind. It is, therefore, advisable for everybody to worship and take care of the respective tree species assigned to them. The therapeutic potential of these nine plant species are explored to combat human diseases (cf. Kodoliker *et al.*, 2023). They also revealed medicinal significance in case Nakshatra plant species.

In a nutshell, sacred or religious plants or trees are important in human welfare. Plant (tree) worship is deeply ingrained in Indian culture. Their selection, site of plantations, day, time or month of worship are also suggested. This religious trend obviously helps conserve our biodiversity *vis-à-vis* biowealth which is presently under unprecedented threats from changing climate, biotic interference, over-exploitation urbanization, industrialization, bioinvasion, etc. It has been rightly reiterated that 'Divine Botany': Universal and useful but under-explored traditions (*cf.* Jain and Kapoor, 2007).

With Grahas (Planets) [*=Exotic]

Sr. No.	Grahas (Planets)	Sanskrit Plant Names	Botanical Name & Family	Habit	Status: Wild (W)/ Cultivated (C)	Nativity & Reference
1	Surya (Sun)	*Arka	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) R.Br. Asclepiadaceae	Shrub	W	Tropical Africa: Chandra Sekar, 2012.
2	Chandra (Moon)	Palasha	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lamk.) Taub. Papilionaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
3	Budha (Mercury)	*Apamarge	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L. Amaranthaceae	Herb	W	i) Tropics: Medakkar & Sharma, 2016. ii) Africa: Singh <i>et al.</i> , 2015.
4	Shukra (Venus)	Udumbara	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L. Moraceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
5	Mangal (Mars)	Khadira	<i>Senegalis catechu</i> (L.f.) P.J.H. Hurter & mcb. [<i>Acacia ctechu</i> (L.f.) Willd.] Mimosaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
6	Guru (Jupiter)	Ashwettha	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L. Moraceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
7	Shani (Saturn)	Shami	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce Mimoceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
8	Rahu (Snake Head)	*Durva	<i>Cynadon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers. Poaceae	Herb	W	i) Tropical Africa: Debnath & Debnath, 2017. ii) Tropical America: Sainkhedia, 2016.
9	Ketu (Snake Tail)	Darbha	<i>Desmostachya bipinnata</i> Stapf Poaceae	Herb	W	Indigenous

Table-II: Plants Associated With Rashi (Sign of Zodiac) [*=Exotic]

Sr. No.	Grahas (Planets)	Sanskrit Plant Names	Botanical Name & Family	Habit	Status: Wild (W)/ Cultivated (C)	Nativity & Reference
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1	Mesha (Aries)	Rakta Chandan	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> L.f. Papilionaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
2	Vrushabha (Taurus)	Saptaparna	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R.Br. Apocynaceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
3	Mithuna (Gemini)	*Panas	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lamk. Moraceae	Tree	C	Indigenous
4	Karka (Cancer)	Palasha	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lamk.) Taub. Papilionaceae	Tre	W	Indigenous
5	Simha (Leo)	Patala	<i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i> (Roxb.) DC. Bignoniaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
6	Karya (Virgo)	Amra	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L. Anacardiaceae	Tree	C	Indigenous
7	Tula (Libra)	Bakula	<i>Mimusops elengi</i> L. Sapotaceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
8	Vrichika (Scorpio)	Khadira	<i>Senesalia catechu</i> (L.f.) P.,J.H. Hurtar [Syn.Acacia catechu (L.f.) Willd.] Mimosaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
9	Dhanu (Sagittarius)	Ashwattha	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L. Moraceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
10	Makara (Caprocon)	Shinshupa	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> Roxb. ex DC. Papilionaceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
11	Kumbha (Aquarius)	Shami	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce Mimosaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
12	Meena (Pisces)	Vata	<i>Ficus bengalensis</i> L. Moraceae	Tree	C	Indigenous

Table-III: Plant species Associated with Nakshatras (Stars) [*=Exotic]

Sr. No.	Grahas (Planets)	Sanskrit Plant Names	Botanical Name & Family	Habit	Status: Wild (W)/ Cultivated (C)	Nativity & Reference
1	Ashwini (Beta Arietis)	Kuchala	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L. Loganiaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
2	Bharani (41 Arietis)	Amalaki	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L. Euphorbiaceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
3	Kritika (Etatauri Alcyone-2)	Udumbara	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L. Moraceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
4	Rohini (Aldebaron)	Jambu	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels Myrtaceae	Tree	C	Indigenous
5	Mrigashira (Lambda)	Khadira	<i>Senesalia catechu</i> (L.f.) P.,J.H. Hurtar	Tree	W	Indigenous

	Orionis)		[Syn.Acacia catechu (L.f.) Willd.] Mimosaceae			
6	Aardra (Gamma)	(i) Shinshupa (ii) Krishna Agaru (iii) Krishna *Kamala	i) <i>Dalbergia sisso</i> Roxb. ex DC. Papilionaceae ii) <i>Acquilaria agallocha</i> Roxb. Thymelaceae iii) <i>Passiflora edulis</i> Sims. Passifloraceae	Tree Tree Climber	W,C W C	i) Indigenous ii) Indigenous iii) Brazil: Patil, 1995; South America: Stewart, 1972.
7	Punarvasu (Beta) Geminorium Pollux)	i) Vamsha ii) *Babbula	i) <i>Bambusa arundinacea</i> Willd. Poacee ii) <i>Vachellia nilotica</i> (L.) P.J.H. Hurtner & Mull. Mimosaceae	Herb Tree	W W	i) Indigenous ii) North-Africa & Arab: Rajagopal & Panigrahi, 1965.
8	Pushya (Delta) Cancri)	Ashwatha	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L. Moraceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
9	Ashlesha (Zeta) Hydare)	Nagakeshara	<i>Mesua ferrea</i> L. Clusiaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
10	Magha (Regulus/ Roleonis)	Vata	<i>Ficus bengalensis</i> L. Moraceae	Tree	C	Indigenous
11	Purva phalguni (Delta) Leonis)	Palasha	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lamk.) Taub. Papilionaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
12	Uttara phalguni (Delta) Leonis)	i) Shami ii) Plaksha	i) <i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce Mimosaceae ii) <i>Ficus lacor</i> Buch.-Ham. Moraceae	Tree Tree	W W	i) Indigenous ii) Indigenous
13	Hasta (Delta) Corvi)	Jaati	<i>Jasminum grandiflorum</i> L. Oleaceae	Climber	C	Indigenous
14	Chitra (Virginis) Spica)	Bilva	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corr. Rutaceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
15	Swati (Alpha) Bootis/ Arcturus)	Arjuna	<i>Terminalia cuneata</i> Roth. [Syn.T.arjuna (Roxb.) Wight & Arn.] Combretaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous
16	Vishakha (Alpha) Librae)	Parijata	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i> L. Oleaceae	Tree	C	Indigenous
17	Anuradha (Delta) Scorpii)	i) Bakula ii) Naga Keshara	i) <i>Mimusops elengi</i> L. Sapotaceae ii) <i>Mesua ferrea</i> L. Clusiaceae	Tree Tree	W, C W	i) Indigenous ii) Indigenous
18	Jeshta (Antres)	i) *Shalmali	i) <i>Bombax ceiba</i> L. (Syb.B.malabaricum DC.) Bombaceae	Tree	W	i) Africa: Gaikwad & Garad, 2015; Brazil to Argentina:

		ii) Nimba	ii) <i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss. Meliaceae	Tree	W, C	Singh <i>et al.</i> , 2015. ii) Indigenous
19	Moola (Lambda Scorpi)	i) Bilva	i) <i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corr. Rutaceae	Tree	W, C	i) Indigenous
		ii)*Argawadha	ii) <i>Cassia fistula</i> L. Caesalpiniaceae	Tree	C	ii) North: Debnath & Debnath, 2017.
		ii) Devadaru	iii) <i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb.) G. Don Pinaceae	Tree	W	ii) Indigenous
20	Purva Ashada (Delta Sagittarii)	i) Ashoka	i) <i>Saraca asoca</i> (Roxb.) de Wilde Caesalpiniaceae	Tree	W, C	i) Indigenous
		ii) Mushkaka	ii) <i>Schrebera swietenoides</i> Roxb. Oleraceae	Tree	W	ii) Indigenous
21	Uttara Ashad (Sigma segittarii)	Panasa	Artocarpus heterphyllus Lamk. Moraceae	Tree	C	Indigenous
22	Shravana (Alpho Aquila Altair)	i) *Arka	i) <i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br. Asclepiadaceae	Shrub	W	i) Tropical Africa: Chandra Sekar, 2012.
		ii) Ashoka	ii) <i>Saraca asoca</i> (Roxb.) de Wilde Caesalpiniaceae	Tree	W, C	ii) Indigenous
		ii) Narikela	iii) <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. Arecaceae	Tree	C	iii) Indigenous
23	Dhanistha (Beta Delphini)	i) Shami	i) <i>Prosopis cineria</i> (L.) Druce. Mimosaceae	Tree	W	i) Indigenous
		ii) Narikela	ii) <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. Arecaceae	Tree	C	ii) Indigenous
24	Shatataraka (Lamda Aqaril)	Kadama	<i>Neolmarckia cadamba</i> (Roxb.) [Syn.Anthocephalus kadamba (Roxb.) Miq.] Rubiaceae	Tree	W, C	Indigenous
25	Purva Bhadrapada (Beta Pegsi/ Markab)	i) Amva	i) <i>Mangifera indica</i> L. Anacardiaceae	Tree	C	i) Indigenous
		ii) Mimba	ii) <i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.juss. Meliaceae	Tree	W, C	ii) Indigenous
26	Uttara Bhadrapada (Gamma Pegasi/ Algenib)	i) Amra	i) <i>Mangifera indica</i> L. Anacardiaceae	Tree	C	i) Indigenous
		ii) Nimba	ii) <i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss. Meliaceae	Tree	W, C	ii) Indigenous
27	Revati (Zeta Piscium)	Madhuka	<i>Madhuca indica</i> J. F. Gmel. Sapotaceae	Tree	W	Indigenous

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